

Translation on Medical Terms into Indonesian

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Abstract--This research reveals the linguistics phenomenon especially translation. Translation in this research is focused on medical and the use of medical technical terms. The problems were formulated into translation procedure on medical terms into Indonesian. The theories of this research were translation theory namely translation procedure by Vinay dan Darbelnet (in Venuti, 2000), theory of semantics (semantic features) by Nida & Taber (1975). Research related to medical linguistics so far is still relatively small and the object of research so far is still in books or library research. This research reveals translations in health terms. The results of this study are the procedures for translating health terms that are reformulated in accordance with research needs. Therefore, research on the translation of health terms necessary.

Keywords: Translation, Medical terms, translation procedures

I. Introduction

Translation is the transfer of language including microlinguistics and macrolinguistics in transferring the meaning of the source language (SL) to the target language (TL). In translation, when viewed microlingually, there is a lexical transfer, grammatical structure, or sound, whereas, macrolinguistically there is a transfer of language that is adjusted, both with speakers and the use of language. In line with this, Larson (1998: 3) explained that translation is basically a change of form. Translation includes the study of lexical, grammatical structures, communication of situations and cultural contexts from SL to TL, analysis of meaning to determine meaning or meaning then reconstruct the same meaning using lexical and grammatical structures that are appropriate to the cultural context of TL. Larson also explained that the translation includes the transfer of meaning from SL to TL or the form from SL is changed into TL form by referring to the semantic structure.

Translation studies that include the equivalence of SL to TL are increasingly important to be developed even more at this time Indonesia is facing an important era that is "Asean Free Trade Era" so that international languages and science cannot be separated from one another. For example, health science has a very rapid development, especially in health services. Paramedics can provide optimal health services if they can communicate in English as a means of international communication, especially in Bali as a tourist destination, and there are many international hospitals. In this connection international cooperation is not only established in hospitals, but also cooperation with overseas health institutions. For example, in the field of midwifery services international cooperation has been established between midwifery institutions in Bali and Australia in the fields of seminars, workshops, clinics or practice land. The seminar and workshop aims to further improve midwifery services in Bali as a tourist destination. Midwives will be able to provide the best service in cooperation or exchange of insights can be continuously improved for the development of science and health services. Besides translation studies can help to improve services because qualified translation can avoid malpractice from the health study.

Research related to medical linguistics so far is still relatively small and the object of research so far is still in books or library research. This research reveals translations in health terms. The results of this study is the procedures for translating health terms that are reformulated in accordance with research needs. Therefore, research on the translation of health terms necessary.

1.2 Problem

In the foregoing it has been stated, that determining the process of translating terms in the field of midwifery is very interesting to study. In this regard, the problems that arise in this study are as follows.

1. What procedures were found in translating health terms into Indonesian?
2. How are the terms translated into Indonesian?

1.3 Research Objectives

Based on the formulation of the problem, the purpose of this study is divided into two types, namely general objectives and special objectives. Each of these objectives can be described as follows.

1.3.1 General Purpose

In general, this research aims to apply and develop critical and in-depth translation studies related to translation procedures that can be accepted by the target audience and can assist the learning process and understanding of the use of English in specific sciences health especially midwifery.

1.3.2 Special Purpose

The specific objectives of the study can be explained as follows.

1. Identify the procedure used by translators in translating health terms especially midwifery from English into Indonesian.
2. Describe the adaptation of meaning components in the translation of the term health, especially midwifery from English to Indonesian.

1.4 Research Benefits

Based on the description of the specific research objectives above, there are several benefits that are expected to be derived from the results of this study. These benefits can be broadly grouped into two types, namely (a) theoretical benefits and (b) practical benefits. The two benefits can be described one by one as follows.

1.4.1 Theoretical Benefits

Theoretically, the results of this study are expected to provide benefits for the following things.

1. Benefits for the development of science in applied language or linguistics. This is important because the implementation of the field of translation studies is applied, especially in translating specific fields of science, namely midwifery.
2. Benefits for the enrichment and availability of reference sources and information in the treasury and the field of translation studies in particular, because the results of this study are expected to be able to add and enrich reference sources about the translation process in specific midwifery science

1.4.2 Practical Benefits

The results of this study are expected to be of practical use for the following matters

1. The benefits for translators in translating health texts, especially midwifery in this study explain the variation of translation along with an analysis of the meaning of each variation of the midwifery terms, so that it can provide options for translators to be more accurate in translating the midwifery terms into TL.
2. Benefits for paramedics related to health sciences, especially midwifery and the English language division, this research can be used as a guide in dealing with foreign patients and improve their knowledge with the existence of translation research in health sciences, especially midwifery, making it easier for them to learn texts in the language English, so that their research can continue to grow and provide international service.
4. Benefits for other researchers who are interested in conducting translation research which until now translation research related to health science especially midwifery is still relatively very rare. The results of

this study can be used as reference material or references in other foreign languages research. In addition, matters or gaps that have not yet been investigated in this study will result in the emergence of special midwifery translation research results with other foreign language research objects.

II. Theoretical Basis

2.1 Translation

Larson (1984: 3) states that translation is the transfer of messages from SL into TL. The meaning is transferred and must be maintained, while the form may be changed. This process is achieved by transferring the form from SL into TL form, with semantic structure. Reiterated that translation is a change of form. The form of a language consists of words, phrases, clauses, sentences and paragraphs.

Translation procedure is a term used by Machali (2000: 62), which is the way or strategy used by translators in translating clauses, words, and so on. In this study, identification of the procedure referred to is the method or strategy used by translators in translating the term health, especially midwifery. Vinay and Darbelnet (in Venuti, 2000) explain that there are seven kinds of translation procedures that are divided into two categories, namely literal translation and oblique translation. Which includes literal translations are: loans (borrowing), calques, and literal translations (literal translation). Oblique translations include: transposition, modulation, equivalence, and adaptation.

2.2 Components of Meaning

The discussion of the components of meaning (meaning components) proposed by Larson (1984: 27-35) is a discussion of how the components of meaning can be described through certain principles or features. In this research, the theory of the components of meaning uses the Semantic Feature (Semantic Feature) popularized by Nida & Taber (1975), and Larson (1984) and explains the translation ideology applied in translating health terms from English into Indonesian. In analyzing the ideology of translation, this study uses the theory of domestication and foreignization popularized by Hatim (2001).

III. Research Methods

This research is literature and field research. The data used in this study consists of 3 categories, namely written data in the form of words, phrases, clauses and sentences taken in the book "Oxford Handbook of Midwifery" and its translation in "The Oxford Midwifery Book", as well as variations in translations of these medical terms. taken from "Dictionary of Hassan Shadily". Analysis of this first category data reveals the translation procedures and translation ideology applied by the translator.

IV. Research Results

The results of the study are divided into research results in the translation and application of health terms in language functions. Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that the procedures for translating health terms from English to Indonesian are used in various translation procedures. Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that the translation procedures that occur are: a) borrowing, b) literal translation, c) calque, d) modulation, e) adaptation. In this research, the formulation of the abbreviation translation procedure for health terms has not been formulated by researchers before, the formulation of the medical abbreviation translation procedure is based on the data phenomenon in this study. The procedure for translating medical abbreviations in this study is divided into: f) translating abbreviations to abbreviations, g) translating abbreviations to abbreviations, and h) translating phrases into phrases for abbreviations.

4.1.1 Borrowing

Borrowing is a translation procedure by means of a word borrowed directly from SL. Molina and Albir (2002: 509) explained that in this lending technique, translators can use two methods, the first is called pure borrowing. In pure borrowing the translator retains the words in SL without making any changes to TL. The

second is called naturalized borrowing, where translators borrow the word SL, but the pronunciation of the word has been adjusted in TL. The term diversion by borrowing techniques is found in the "Oxford Handbook of Midwifery" and "The Oxford Midwifery Book".

1.	The basis of <i>massage</i> is touch, which may midwives incorporate into their care of the laboring woman. (Oxford Handbook of Midwifery, pg 242)	Dasar <i>masase</i> adalah sentuhan, yang banyak digunakan oleh banyak bidan dalam perannya ekadalam merawat wanita bersalin. (Buku Kebidanan Oxford, pg 206)
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Data (1) shows naturalized borrowing, i.e. there is a word lending technique in SL *massage*, but the pronunciation of the word has been adjusted in TL *massage*. However, there are also equivalent words that are commonly used for the word *massage* in the Indonesian language contained in the TL which is *massage* (SL) translated into *Pijat* (TL). In this case borrowing used in specific midwifery.

The semantic feature shows the description of *massage* in the Winson Midwifery Dictionary (2005: 253) is the activity of rubbing or squeezing the body to help relaxation, stimulate circulation and excretion, and decrease blood pressure. During labor, some mothers want to be rubbed on their abdomen. The semantic feature is notated (+), while '*massage*' Sugono et al (2008: 872) in KBBI explain the word '*massage*' to mean *massage*, so that '*massage*' in TL does not yet contain complete medical elements such as the word '*massage*', so the semantic feature is notated (-). '*Massase*' is a loan term from English that is used in medical science, '*massase*' is derived from the word *massage*. When used in translation is done by naturalized borrowing, so that the word *massage* is no longer used, but adjusted to the spelling and pronunciation in TL, in Indonesian there are no consonants consecutive ss so that in the word '*masase*' only one is retained. In addition, the pronunciation of 'ge' in *massage* is not spoken, but the phoneme used is adjusted to the pronunciation of the TL.

The translation in Hasan Shadily's dictionary (2007: 380) containing *massage* (SL) is translated as *massage* (TL), indicating the application of ideology of domestication in the translation. *Massase* (TL) in the "Oxford Midwifery Book" still contains foreign elements and shows the application of foreignization in translation.

4.1.2 Literal Translation

Literal translation is done word for word. There is a literal translation found in the translation of midwifery terms from English into Indonesian in the Oxford Handbook of Midwifery and the translation in Buku Kebidanan Oxford

2	A <i>midwife</i> is a person who, having been regularly admitted to a midwifery educational programme, duly recognized in the country in which it is located, has successfully completed the prescribed course of studies in midwifery and has acquired the requisite qualifications	<i>Bidan</i> adalah seseorang yang telah mengikuti program pendidikan kebidanan standar, sebagaimana yang diakui di negara tempatnya berada, telah berhasil menyelesaikan program studi yang diprogramkan dalam kebidanan dan mendapatkan kualifikasi yang diperlukan untuk terdaftar dan/atau mendapat lisensi secara
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	to be registered and/or legally licensed to practice midwifery (Oxford Handbook of Midwifery, pg4)	ukumuntukmelaksanakanpraktik kebidanan (BukuKebidanan Oxford, pg 3)
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Data (2) shows that the translation is done by word from BSu into BSa, namely a midwife (BSu) translated by midwife (BSa), so that the translation can be categorized as a literal translation. The 'a' article in BSa is not translated so that in BSa there is missing information.

The semantic feature shows a description of midwife, is a person who handles normal deliveries and provides professional medical services. This, in line with the definition set by WHO in Winson (2008: 268), is that a midwife is a person who follows a routine midwifery education program, as recognized in the country where the program has successfully completed all midwifery studies programs and has obtained qualifications that are required to be registered and / or get a legal license to practice midwifery. She must be able to provide the supervision, care and advice needed for women during the period of pregnancy, childbirth and postpartum, being in charge of labor and caring for newborns. The care provided includes preventive measures, detection and abnormal conditions in mother and child, seeking medical help and taking emergency measures if there is no medical help. He has important duties in counseling and health education, not only for patients but also for families and the community. His duties include antenatal education and preparation for parenting and extend to specific gynecological areas, family planning and child care. He can practice in hospitals, clinics, health units, domicile or in various other health services.

The translation in Hasan Shadily's dictionary (2007: 380) containing midwife (SL) is translated as a dukun beranak, it shows the application of the ideology of domestication in the translation. Dukun beranak help patients in traditional ways and do not take institutional education in the learning process.

4.1.3 Kalke (Calque)

Vinay and Darbelnet (in Venuti, 2000) describe a BSu word or phrase translated and used directly in BSa. This procedure has a special characteristic, that is, the interference of the BSu structure in the BSa and the translation is done literally.

3	Abdominal assessment of uterine growth at each <i>antenatal visit</i> takes into account the estimated gestational age calculated from the expected birthdate (Oxford Handbook of Midwifery, pg 16)	Pengkajian abdomen untukmendeteksipeetumbuh an uterus di setiap <i>kunjunganantenatal</i> per lumemperhitungkanperkiraanusiagestasi yang dihitungdaritaksiranpartus (BukuKebidanan Oxford, pg 11)
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Data (3) shows that the antenatal visit phrase is translated directly into *kunjungan antenatal* in TL, so the translation of data (3) shows the calque, namely there is interference of the English in the TL the word *antenatal* is still in the English, meanwhile the word *visit* is translated into *kunjungan*. So that, it seen that interference occur in the TL.

Although there is an interface in the TL, the sematic feature shows the equivalent in meaning from BSu to BSa.

4.1.4 Modulation

Modulation is a translation procedure that changes perspective. Or in other words in this translation procedure experiences a variety of forms. Molina and Albir (2002: 509) explain that the change in perspective is lexical or structural. There is a translation with modulation translation procedure found in the translation of midwifery terms from English into Indonesian in the Oxford Handbook of Midwifery and the translation in the Oxford Midwifery Book which is described as follows.

4	The midwife is recognized as a responsible and accountable professional who works in a partnership with <i>women</i> to give the necessary support, care and advice during pregnancy, labour and the postpartum period, to conduct births on the midwife's own responsibility and to provide care for the newborn and the infant. (Oxford Handbook of Midwifery, pg 4)	Bidanharusmampumemberikan supervise, perawatan, dan informasi yang diperlukan kepada ibu selama periode kehamilan, persalinan dan pascanatal untuk membimbing elahiranata tanggungjawabnya sendiri, dan untuk merawat bayi baru lahir dan bayi (Buku Kebidanan Oxford, pg 3)
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Data (4) shows that women in (SL) are translated as mothers (TL). This shows that there is a shift of perspective on TL. In the text shows "midwives must be able to provide supervision, care and information needed to the mother during the pregnancy period" so that the intended mother is of course the prospective mother (woman who is pregnant / during the pregnancy period). Medforth (2006) explained that related to midwifery counseling for women and mothers is the object of examination in general. Female patients can generally be divided into single women, married women, expectant mothers or mothers, so in this case the TL translation of prospective mothers can be used.

Semantic features show women (pl), describe adult women who are or are not married, have or have not given birth. Mother according to the KBBI (2002: 416) is a mature woman, married, and has given birth to someone.

4.1.5 Adaptation

Vinay and Darbelnet (in Venuti, 2000) explain that adaptation is a translation procedure that replaces SL elements with elements that are accepted and known in TL. In other words the translator replaces the SL cultural elements with cultural elements that have the same characteristics in TL and those cultural elements are already familiar to the target audience. There is a translation with adaptation translation techniques found in the translation of midwifery terms from English into Indonesian in the book "Oxford Handbook of Midwifery" and its translation in "The Oxford Midwifery Book", which is described as follows.

5.	Feel a sensation of wanting to <i>bear down</i> , although the cervix is not quite fully dilated-there is no rationale for preventing women from bearing down if they so desire (Oxford Handbook of Midwifery, pg 266)	Merasasensasiinginmengejan,meskipunservikstidakcukupterdilatasiseocarapenuh-tidakadarasionaluntukmencegahwanitamengejanjikamerekamenginginkannya. (BukuKebidanan Oxford, Pg 230)
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Data (5) shows the use of adaptation techniques, namely the word bear down which literally according to the English-Indonesian Dictionary Hassan Shadilly, 2007: 57) implies BSu trying hard. However, in the medical text (midwifery) the word bear down may contain the meaning of straining used in the health text (midwifery), namely changes in women's physical behavior and attitudes that provide visual clues that characterize the end of the first stage of labor and the beginning of the second stage, in this case women can feel the sensation of wanting to push.

The semantic feature shows the bear down description in the Winson Midwifery Dictionary (2005: 253) is the strong / contraction felt by the mother during the second stage of labor, when the mother pushes, both involuntarily and with additional force to push the baby through the birth canal.

V. Research Findings

There are two findings in this study. The findings are described in accordance with the analysis in answering the problem and based on the theory used in analyzing the problem. There are two findings, namely (1) theoretical findings Theoretical findings directly contribute to linguistics, especially translation. Translation in this study focuses on medical translation.

The systematics laid out in this study includes the procedures applied in translating the terms and abbreviations of health from English into Indonesian. Mapping procedures and methods of medical terms and abbreviations can be done after classification or phenomena of existing data. There are five procedures found in the data in the study, namely (1) borrowing, (2) literal translation, (3) calculation, (4) modulation, (5) adaptation. Then specifically for the translation of medical syntax systematics mapped in accordance with the phenomenon of the data found.

VI. Conclusions and Suggestions

Conclusions and suggestions in this study are based on analysis and findings as answers to the formulation of the problems raised in the study. There are two linguistic theories discussed in this study, namely (1) translation

6.1 Conclusion

The conclusions that can be drawn in this study are carried out from the process of data collection, data analysis in accordance with the theory of translation and language function, so the conclusions that can be drawn are as follows.

1) Translation of Medical Terms

There are five main procedures found in translating medical terms into Indonesian, namely: borrowing, literal translation, calculating, modulation, and adaptation.

6.2 Suggestions

a. Contribution in Linguistics

- 1) For other researchers interested in Linguistics
This research can be used as a reference source for other researchers interested in researching the field of translation, especially health. In addition, the development of translation procedures which are the findings in this study can also be applied in translations other than health. Other researchers can use the theory development procedure for abbreviating specific terms into the translation of other specific texts. There are several studies that can be done further:
 1. Specific term translation procedures by using the development of acronym translation procedures into Indonesian in other fields such as law, tourism and so on.

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